

MERGE

MEASURING WHAT MATTERS

Policy pathways to sustainable and
inclusive wellbeing

Deliverable D10.2:

Revised plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

WP10-11 Communication, dissemination and exploitation

Version 1.0 (31.05.2025)

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About

Achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the European Union's policies on environmental and social sustainability requires a comprehensive measure of human progress beyond gross domestic product (GDP). However, fragmented evidence and a lack of consensus on alternative approaches hinder the establishment of policy goals that promote sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (SIW) and the monitoring of progress.

MERGE addresses these challenges by fostering dialogue, co-creation, and knowledge exchange, bridging cutting-edge research and policy practice. Through a consortium of leading researchers and key communities, including the EU-funded research initiatives SPES, ToBe, WISE Horizons, REAL, MultiFutures, MAPS, WISER, and SWINS, MERGE aims to establish a multidisciplinary community and network of technical, policy, and civil society actors.

The Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) plays a key role in maximising the impact of the project, ensuring that project outputs reach and influence a wide audience of relevant stakeholders. This document includes actions to ensure the successful promotion of the project and its outcomes over the grant period.

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1. Introduction

Achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the European Union's policies on environmental and social sustainability requires a comprehensive measure of human progress beyond gross domestic product (GDP). However, fragmented evidence and a lack of consensus on alternative approaches hinder the establishment of policy goals that promote *sustainable and inclusive wellbeing* (SIW) and the monitoring of progress.

MERGE addresses these challenges by fostering dialogue, co-creation, and knowledge exchange, bridging cutting-edge research and policy practice. Through a consortium of leading researchers and key communities, including the EU-funded research initiatives SPES, ToBe, WISE Horizons, REAL, MultiFutures, MAPS, WISER, and SWINS, MERGE aims to establish a multidisciplinary community and network of technical, policy, and civil society actors. These collaborations seek to develop widely accepted indicators and frameworks for measuring multidimensional wellbeing within planetary boundaries at the EU, Member State, and global levels.

MERGE offers a transformative solution to the longstanding reliance on GDP-centric progress measurement, paving the way for global sustainability. In particular, MERGE focuses on promoting an economy that supports sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (SIW) which prioritises human and planetary health, ensures equal opportunities for all, and supports long-term prosperity without depleting natural resources or deepening social inequalities. The terminology has been collectively agreed upon within the consortium as part of thinking about the communication strategy.

The Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) plays an instrumental role in maximising the impact of the project, increasing its visibility, and ensuring that project outputs reach and influence a wide audience of relevant stakeholders. This document includes actions to ensure the successful promotion of the project and its outcomes over the grant period. By uniting a diverse array of research initiatives and stakeholders, including civil society organisations (CSOs), researchers, policymakers, and statistical bureaus, MERGE is uniquely positioned to translate cutting-edge research into practical strategies.

This is a living document, designed to be revisited and updated throughout the lifespan of MERGE to reflect emerging needs, activities, and tools. We are now revising it as planned in Month 17 of the project, with the next formal update scheduled for Month 36 (D11.1). Unlike the original plan, which focused primarily on communication and

dissemination, this updated version also covers exploitation and the expected impact of MERGE beyond the project's duration.

1.1. Purpose and Scope

Project objectives:

- **Objective 1:** The primary objective of MERGE is to propose a unified set of indicators for measuring multidimensional SIW. This includes summarising indicators already known to statistical institutions and identifying new relevant metrics beyond GDP to provide a more comprehensive understanding of societal progress.
- **Objective 2:** MERGE strives to offer evidence-based research on SIW indicators. In doing so, the project consortium will attempt to identify the scientific foundations of the indexes or indicator dashboards.
- **Objective 3:** MERGE aims to provide policymakers with actionable insights and support informed decision-making processes at various levels of governance. Thus, MERGE will compile a database which assigns indicators to political goals and describes indicators according to the likelihood of uptake in policymaking.
- **Objective 4:** Through its focus on a SIW economy, MERGE aims to contribute to the advancement of sustainability goals. By shifting the emphasis from GDP-centric progress measurement to a more holistic approach, the initiative aims to promote sustainable development practices.

The strategy for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication activities is designed to leverage a wide array of communication channels (such as LinkedIn, project's website, and newsletter), tailored to engage the diverse network of stakeholders involved. By harnessing proactive support from the entire consortium, the plan endeavours to effectively spotlight and disseminate the project's key findings and achievements.

1.2. The structure of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan

This CDE-document is divided into the following sections:

1. **Introduction** – Providing a high-level overview of the document, which outlines the overall Dissemination and Communication Strategy.
2. **MERGE partners** – Providing an overview of the main partners involved in the MERGE project.
3. **MERGE sibling projects** – Presenting the sibling projects of MERGE.
4. **Target audiences** – Identifying the primary target audiences for the communication and dissemination activities of MERGE and outlining specific messaging and engagement strategies tailored to each audience segment.
5. **Tone of voice** – Establishing the desired tone and style for communication and dissemination activities within MERGE.
6. **Key pillars of the CDE strategy** – Describing the strategic approach and methodology currently undertaken by MERGE, including communication channels, dissemination strategies, planned exploitation activities, and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.
7. **Conclusions** – Summarising key takeaways and insights from the CDE strategy for MERGE.

2. MERGE partners

The MERGE consortium comprises a diverse group of partners:

Research partners:

- Tampere University (acting as coordinator)
- PIN Soc.Cons.A R L.
- Universitat de Barcelona
- Universiteit Gent
- University College London
- Università Degli Studi di Ferrara IT
- Universiteit Leiden

Technical partners:

- UK Office for National Statistics
- Institut d'Estadística de Catalunya

Policy partners:

- Zoe-Institute for Future-fit Economies (acting as co-lead)
- European Policy Centre
- Demos Research Institute/Demos Helsinki (CDE lead)
- Plateforme des ONG européennes du secteur social
- Joint Research Centre.

Civil society partners:

- Research and Degrowth International
- Wellbeing Economy Alliance

3. MERGE sibling projects

"Sibling projects" denote related endeavours that share common goals, methodologies, and thematic focuses, forming a network of interconnected efforts. Within the framework of collaborative research initiatives, MERGE has four (4) sibling projects, including SPES, ToBe, WISE-Horizons, and REAL, and functions as a coordination and support action for them. Among MERGE consortium partners there are participants in all the four sibling

projects, and these projects comprise key projects researching connecting themes with MERGE with Horizon Europe or European Research Council funding. Below, we present the original 4 sibling projects; however, during the 1,5h years of the project, we have expanded the collaboration to include in total 8 projects with an addition of [MultiFutures](#), [SWINS](#), [MAPS](#) and [WISER](#).

SPES (<https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/>) generates new knowledge and evidence about the nexus between economic growth, human flourishing, and sustainability. The objective is to elaborate a novel integrated framework on sustainability transition to reconcile productivity enhancement and value-generation with inclusiveness and environmental protection.

ToBe (www.toberesearch.eu) focuses on integrated policy models and transformative indicators with the aim of building an understanding of a sustainable wellbeing economy by combining green growth and postgrowth initiatives. It studies how mindsets, indicators, innovations and policies could work towards the sustainability paradigm and pathways leading there.

WISE-Horizons (<https://wisehorizons.world>) creates a synthesis of the current post-growth initiatives. It clarifies the concepts and the determinants of trade-offs/synergies for policy and society. The project will create environmental, social and economic indicators in a novel and open WISE accounting/database.

REAL (<https://www.realpostgrowth.eu/>) offers pathways for universal human well-being removed from dependence on economic growth. It focuses on possibilities, policies, politics, and provisioning and how these could be implemented in practice. The project develops equitable North-South scenarios, human wellbeing models, and post-growth policy packages.

Coordinating CDE activities with these projects enables MERGE to leverage their outputs and insights to inform our communication strategies and engagement efforts. Additionally, MERGE CDE can provide valuable support to these projects by drawing on their findings to enhance our communication and engagement initiatives. This reciprocal relationship fosters synergies and collaboration across multiple initiatives, ultimately contributing to more comprehensive and impactful outcomes.

So far, we have been convening monthly meetings with the CDE partners in sibling projects for important project updates and potential synergies and support in the CDE effort. Apart from sharing the best CDE practices and amplifying outreach for one another, MERGE and its sibling projects have successfully coordinated CDE activities, e.g., promoting the [competitiveness letter](#) co-signed by the projects' leaders or collaborating in a joint newsletter sent out by MERGE.

4. Target audiences

Effective communication involves delivering pertinent information to the appropriate audience at the optimal moment and in a suitable format. It is also essential to identify all relevant stakeholders and understand their interests in order to achieve the project's goals. Stakeholder mapping is crucial, as it aligns target audiences with communication objectives and guides engagement activities. This comprehensive mapping enables strategic planning and allows communication strategies to be tailored to each audience segment from the outset, supporting the iterative development of key messages.

In Work Packages 2 and 3, stakeholder mapping was carried out to identify and reach key actors. In WP2, the consortium conducted extensive mapping (over 300 stakeholders) of technical stakeholders working on data collection, national accounting, and statistics to measure and monitor wellbeing, sustainability, and resilience. This included national statistical offices or institutes in all EU member states, statistical departments in national governments, relevant Eurostat and Joint Research Centre (Knowledge for Policy Competence) working groups or task forces, statistical departments and groups within international organisations (e.g., the OECD, the UN), research networks, consortium partners' own networks, and other relevant fora.

In WP3, the consortium conducted similarly extensive mapping of policy actors involved in developing beyond GDP policy frameworks and SIW indicators. This included high-level and senior political representatives, policymakers, and working-level civil servants across all EU member state governments and EU institutions, including the Joint Research Centre. The aim of this mapping was to establish an overarching network of over 300 policy actors, inform them about the MERGE project, and engage them in forthcoming activities. In practice, we reached out to key stakeholders with invitations to join the network, and we have been continuously engaging with them through meetings and co-creation workshops, sharing research findings as part of dissemination and exploitation efforts.

We are now revising this document, as planned, in Month 17. Thanks to the extensive stakeholder mapping carried out in WP2 and WP3, and additional engagement and outreach through discussions and networking, we have been able to reach stakeholders across all previously identified priority groups. Looking ahead to the final 1.5 years of the project, particular emphasis will be placed on dissemination and exploitation, working closely with stakeholders we are now in contact with. The focus will be on co-creating useful materials, collecting feedback on our work, and treating the collaborative process as equally important as the final outputs – such as toolboxes or policy briefs – thereby supporting broader uptake and relevance, even beyond MERGE.

The MERGE six distinct target groups for CDE activities are depicted below, having remained the same as they were when we started: Policymakers, Academia and research, Economic CSOs, General public, Statistical offices, and Media.

4.1. Policymakers

Policymakers are responsible for designing, negotiating, and implementing policies at national, EU, and international levels. They operate under political, administrative, and legal constraints while responding to shifting societal demands. Their work shapes the institutional and regulatory landscape in which economic and sustainability frameworks are developed and applied.

As we strive to promote indicators that enable us to assess progress in the area of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing, policymakers' engagement is crucial in our endeavour. Through collaborative efforts, we aim to increase the usage of these indicators in decision-making, governance frameworks, and policies.

Examples of actors in the group: This group includes ministries in EU Member States and key departments within the European Commission, such as the Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV), Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROW), Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL), Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs (DG ECFIN), Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), and Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE). It also includes agencies such as the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC). We also targeted international organisations including the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), International Labour Organization (ILO), United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions

Network (UN SDSN), United Nations University (UNU), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA).

Goals of CDE activities:

- Increase awareness of MERGE's work on sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (SIW).
- Build trust and long-term relationships with policymakers across governance levels.
- Engage actors in co-creation.
- Provide narratives and content that support relevant policy goals and public alignment.
- Ensure MERGE outputs are relevant for ongoing policy processes.

We engaged policymakers through outreach, tailored messages, different types of written forms (e.g., a letter on the competitiveness compass) and events (e.g., MERGE kick-off conference). As a result, we established working relationships with selected individuals and institutions and received feedback on project deliverables. We will continue working with engaged actors – e.g., Members of the European Parliament (MEPs), Commission staff, and national ministries – to co-create relevant tools and frameworks. The focus will shift more toward dissemination and exploitation, ensuring MERGE outputs align with real policy needs.

4.2. Academia and Research

MERGE is dedicated to enhancing academic understanding beyond GDP measures through interdisciplinary research. Our primary goal is to disseminate MERGE's results to researchers, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Examples of actors in the group: Academic institutions and networks such as the International Society for Ecological Economics (ISEE), International Society for Industrial Ecology (ISIE), European Society for Ecological Economics (ESEE), Corvinus University of Budapest, University of Ghent, University of Pisa, University of Vienna, Université libre de Bruxelles (Institute for Environmental Management and Land-Use Planning – IGEAT), ICHEC Brussels Management School, Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU-Wien), Centre for the Understanding of Sustainable Prosperity (CUSP), Ecologic Institute, Institute for European Environmental Policy (IEEP), Veblen Institute for Economic Reforms, Sustainable Europe Research Institute (SERI), Stockholm Resilience Centre, Open Society Foundations (OSF), Bruegel, International Labour Organization's Global Accelerator on

Jobs and Social Protection for Just Transitions (ILO GAIN), Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP), World Inequality Lab, Global Assessment for a New Economics (GANE), and the Institute for New Economic Thinking at the University of Oxford (INET Oxford).

Goals of CDE activities:

- Disseminate MERGE research findings to academic audiences.
- Strengthen interdisciplinary exchange on beyond-GDP and SIW economy topics.
- Contribute to academic publications and open-access research outputs.
- Build long-term collaboration networks for continued knowledge development.
- Search for opportunities for joint funding applications within similar themes.

We produce high-quality research materials based on project data and share findings at numerous international conferences (e.g. the OECD Wellbeing Forum, the ISEE-Degrowth 2025 Conference) members use these events to present results, exchange ideas, and meet in person. Academic articles based on MERGE outputs are being prepared and submitted to peer-reviewed, open-access journals via platforms such as [ZENODO](#) (EU Open research repository). We will continue participating in relevant academic conferences and forums. These efforts support both scholarly impact and transparency.

4.3. Economic CSOs

Civil society organisations working to reshape economic thinking through sustainability-aligned indicators and participatory approaches. These actors often operate across research, advocacy, and local mobilisation, contributing to both policy and public understanding of beyond GDP frameworks.

Examples of actors in the group: Organisations such as the Green Economy Coalition, Postgrowth Alliance, Club of Rome, Rethinking Economics, CEEweb for Biodiversity, Climate Action Network (CAN) Europe, Partners for a New Economy (P4NE), New Economics Foundation, One Project, and the Economic Change Unit. The Wellbeing Economy Alliance (WEAll), a partner in the MERGE consortium, has served as a key link to this broader network. Additionally, a partner and a co-lead in the MERGE consortium, ZOE Institute, chairs the EU Wellbeing Coalition.

Goals of CDE activities for this group

- To support exchange between researchers and civil society actors on the development and use of SIW indicators.
- To strengthen the relevance and legitimacy of indicators and policies through participatory inputs.

- To build informal connections that may lead to more structured collaboration.
- To ensure MERGE remains aligned with broader societal debates and advocacy work in this space.

During the first half of the project, MERGE partners have taken part in joint writing processes and hosted events (e.g., the [MERGE kickoff conference](#)), with commentaries (e.g., "[Productivity for what](#)" commentary piece) and participation in civil society. Informal exchanges and meetings have taken place to explore alignment and opportunities for cooperation, and we will continue to explore this further moving more deeply into exploitation.

4.4. General Public

Individuals with an interest in sustainability, social justice, and economic alternatives, including university students, active citizens, and members of civil society. These groups often seek accessible ways to understand the future of economic governance.

Examples of actors in the group: Students and faculty members from participating universities and European business schools; members or audiences reached through networks such as the European Youth Forum, European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC), SOLIDAR, WECF, CONCORD, and Global Call to Action Against Poverty (GCAP).

Goals of CDE activities for this group:

- To make the concept and implications of SIW indicators and policies accessible and engaging for non-expert audiences.
- To provide entry points for participation and co-production of knowledge, especially for students and younger generations.
- To encourage broader public reflection on economic alternatives that support wellbeing and sustainability.
- To support integration of MERGE themes into teaching and learning across partner institutions.

MERGE has been and will continue hosting open online events that were widely promoted via social media channels, encouraging participation from any interested individual. Engagement has taken place through informal follow-up discussions via email and LinkedIn, including directing interested individuals to relevant experts within the consortium (for example, MERGE and its sibling project WISE-Horizons were introduced by a consortium member in the [SynCrisis final conference](#) organised by the European Confederation of Independent Trade Unions (CESI).

4.5. Statistical Offices

Public bodies and international institutions are responsible for producing and coordinating official statistics. These organisations are central to ensuring the credibility, comparability, and practical use of economic indicators across national and global levels.

Examples of actors in the group: National statistical offices of the Netherlands, Germany, Slovenia, Finland, Spain, Italy, and the United Kingdom; Eurostat; UN Statistics Division (UNSTATS); United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD).

Goals of CDE activities for this group:

- To encourage dialogue around evolving data needs and the role of SIW metrics.
- To explore collaborative approaches for bridging data gaps and developing new indicators.
- To strengthen the technical robustness and policy relevance of MERGE outputs.
- To ensure that new indicators can be integrated into official data ecosystems over time.

The MERGE engagement with this group has been ongoing particularly within WP5 (Technical and data deep-dives). As per the stakeholder mapping in WP 2, the stakeholders were initially identified. Building on from past collaborations, experts from statistical offices are planned to be invited to workshops and discussions going further.

4.6. Media

Journalists, editors, and media professionals working across EU-level and national outlets with an interest in economic, environmental, and social policy. These actors shape public discourse and help translate complex research into accessible narratives for broader audiences.

Examples of actors in the group: EU-level outlets such as *Politico*, *Euractiv*, *Euronews*, and *Dods Briefing*; national media including *Der Spiegel* (Germany) and *Helsingin Sanomat* (Finland); additional thematic or sector-specific platforms where MERGE topics are relevant.

Goals of CDE activities for this group

- To enhance visibility and public understanding of SIW indicators and sustainable economic frameworks.

- To support journalists and editors in accessing timely, accurate, and relevant material on emerging economic thinking.
- To foster thoughtful and informed public conversations on new economic paradigms.
- To ensure MERGE deliverables are communicated in an engaging and policy-relevant manner.

During the first 1,5 years of MERGE, press releases have been prepared and distributed around key MERGE deliverables. These efforts have led to some media uptake, including a published piece in [EU Observer](#). MERGE social media channels have been used to share insights and findings with a broader audience. Steps were taken to establish MERGE as a source of commentary on SIW. Initial recognition in selected media outlets helped test narrative angles and public resonance. Moving further, we will engage more deeply in this stakeholder group, developing media-friendly materials including op-eds, visuals, expert commentary and gaining valuable feedback from journalists with connections to the topic.

5. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy of MERGE

5.1. Objectives

The primary aim of the MERGE Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan is to ensure widespread dissemination and utilisation of the project's results. The plan outlines specific objectives and corresponding implementation strategies to accomplish this goal.

Communication objectives of MERGE are the following:

- Increase understanding of beyond GDP indicators within the data and policy stream through active network activities, publishing and disseminating project findings, attending conferences and events with other stakeholders and European projects, and training activities.
- Increase public acceptance and ensure engagement through workshops, policy labs, meetings, training, social media, newsletters, video/online debates, presentations, and conferences.
- Engage the media and citizens to raise awareness of new economic measures, beyond GDP indicators, to raise their social acceptability and mainstreaming.
- Utilise digital platforms and social media channels to amplify project messaging and reach a wider audience, fostering online communities and discussions beyond GDP indicators and sustainable development goals.

Dissemination objectives of MERGE are the following:

- Disseminate the databases and policy recommendations to NGOs, policymakers and researchers in collaboration with other stakeholders and European projects, along with training activities.
- Share project outcomes and best practices with relevant initiatives, projects, and networks across Europe and globally to strengthen partnerships and collaboration.
- Promote the active involvement of relevant stakeholders and raise public awareness through the [MERGE website](#), a platform of policy and technical material including policy briefs, datasets, and research papers.
- Provide evidence-based policy recommendations to policymakers and statistical offices.

In practice, MERGE disseminates news, experiments, research findings, and events from sources beyond its work, to gather various relevant streams into a joint dialogue and action beyond GDP.

After building the audience through communication measures, the dissemination activities in MERGE paved the way for the exploitation of results. The impact pathways are designed to sustainably maximise the project's impact beyond the project's timeline to ensure long-term impact through research publications and joint projects, learning materials and training, policy briefs, and roadmaps.

5.2. Tone of voice

The tone of voice describes the way MERGE communicates in its promotional channels. It does not apply to scientific publications, policy briefs, or other material produced for specific expert audiences.

These elements are the basis of MERGE's tone of voice:

- Transparent, ensuring that our message is easily understood and resonates with our diverse audience.
- Sincere, marking our commitment to communicate based on our best available expert knowledge on the topic
- Inclusive, open dialogue and collaboration, welcoming diverse perspectives and ideas.
- Approachable yet professional, conveying expertise while remaining accessible to all.

5.3. Targeted messages

MERGE is based on principles of collaboration and co-creation with various stakeholder groups and the wider society. As such, key messages tailored for specific groups will be collaboratively developed and refined throughout the project, informed by ongoing interactions and insights gained. The messages below reflect our current understanding and are subject to evolution as the project progresses.

- *For statisticians:* MERGE harmonises data and gathers cutting-edge insights into measurement practice to empower statisticians with more rigorous and effective tools to measure what really matters.
- *For the academic community:* MERGE brings diverse voices across and beyond academia to advance the field beyond GDP economics and create breakthroughs in knowledge and policy impact.
- *For policymakers:* MERGE develops advanced policy solutions and indicators, identifying novel ways of tackling the most pressing societal challenges.
- *For civil society organisations:* MERGE builds a network of alliances to co-create narratives, strategies and tools to work together towards sustainable and inclusive wellbeing for all.
- *For businesses:* MERGE offers new ways of understanding and measuring social and environmental impact, as well as greater opportunities to align business practice with purpose.
- *For individuals:* MERGE provides information and resources on the latest developments in beyond GDP measurement and policy, and gives a pragmatic vision for achieving sustainable and inclusive well-being.

5.4. Visual identity

The MERGE logo and style guide are presented below. These materials and guidelines for utilising the MERGE visual identity have been distributed to the consortium members. Furthermore, templates for text and presentations have been developed based on the visual identity and distributed to the consortium members.

STYLE GUIDE

THE LOGO

COLOURS

STYLE GUIDE

TYPOGRAPHY

Nunito Sans Black 900
Logo
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!?"%&()*+=+...,<>

Nunito Sans ExtraBold 800
Headings, titles
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!?"%&()*+=+...,<>

Nunito Sans Light 300
Content
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!?"%&()*+=+...,<>

Nunito Sans Light 300 Italic
Content emphasis, quotation
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!?"%&()*+=+...,<>

Nunito Sans SemiBold 600
Content strong
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!?"%&()*+=+...,<>

Nunito Sans SemiBold 600 Italic
Content special
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!?"%&()*+=+...,<>

TYPE SCALE

3.052rem/54.93px
Heading 1

2.441rem/43.95px
Heading 2

1.953rem/35.16px
Heading 3

1.563rem/28.13px
Heading 4

1.25rem/22.5px
Heading 5

1rem/18.00px
Heading 6

1rem/18.00px
Body copy

0.8rem/14.4px
Small

ICONS

5.5. Key channels for impacts

The implementation of the CDE plan is centred around three fundamental channels: the newsletter (whose subscription link is presented on MERGE website), the LinkedIn network, and the project website. Together, these components form the structural foundation of our strategic approach to CDE, ensuring a cohesive and effective dissemination of information, engagement with our network, and exploitation of project outcomes.

- **The newsletter** is created to encapsulate a broad spectrum of information, merging insights from the MERGE initiative, associated projects, and beyond.
- [The LinkedIn network](#) is utilised to foster collaboration, enabling us to share and participate in discussions with various actors.
- [The project website](#) is designated as the central repository for materials, ensuring their preservation for future reference. It also functions as a gateway for new contacts and network expansion, effectively serving as a cornerstone for our outreach and engagement efforts within MERGE.

More details on specific platforms and actions are outlined in the following chapters.

It's important to note that X will not be among our primary channels. Our decision is rooted in the observation that the platform has evolved in ways that no longer align optimally with our communication objectives, becoming less relevant and more challenging to use effectively for our purposes. This choice reflects our strategic commitment to selecting communication channels that best support our goals of effective information dissemination and meaningful engagement with our audience.

For publishing and dissemination purposes, we utilise the [MERGE Zenodo](#) (EU Open Research Repository) page.

5.5.1. Newsletter

To effectively manage the MERGE project newsletter, we prioritise building and engaging a strong community of followers who share our project's goals and vision. Our newsletters serve as a vital tool in keeping both our community of practice and the wider public informed about MERGE's progress and updates.

The newsletter delivers insightful content directly to subscribers' inboxes, covering various topics relevant to the project's objectives. The newsletter consists of subtopics:

1. **Greetings from MERGE:** including updates from all WPs and scanning what is coming next;
2. **Recent MERGE outputs:** including scientific, policy, and popular publications, webinars;
3. **World around MERGE:** including relevant news, policy process developments, EU & beyond GDP-themed articles and events, convenings, and workshops relevant to the audience, but not restricted to MERGE only.

Subscribing to the newsletter is simple and can be done via the MERGE website and beyond, for instance, through attending the project's online events. The newsletter content is put together by Demos Helsinki, but to ensure relevant content from all WP's it is essential that relevant people from all WP's contribute to the newsletter writing. The style of the newsletter is clear, concise, and informative, with an optimal length of approximately 200–500 words per piece.

In the first half of the project, MERGE sent five newsletters to the external audience, with key content encompassing all three subtopics presented above. The subscription number is 260 (up to 5/2025), and the opening rate for each newsletter is always above

55%, with one newsletter achieving a significant 80% opening rate. This is an indicator of MERGE's interest, value, and relevance to its target audience. Notably, one of the newsletters was a joint effort of MERGE and its sibling projects that included their greetings, research work, and upcoming events. This effort shows the potential for MERGE's newsletter channel to expand and elevate similar actors' interest and essential work in the beyond-GDP field.

5.5.2. LinkedIn

Our LinkedIn strategy is designed to enhance engagement, foster connections, and promote the project's mission of advancing sustainable economic indicators. We aim to establish a professional network of policymakers and technical experts on LinkedIn, serving as a practical outcome of the networks built in other work packages. The aim for this network is to continue existing and evolving beyond the project's conclusion, becoming a hub for sharing insights and connecting with key actors in promoting sustainable and inclusive wellbeing .

We established the MERGE LinkedIn page ([linkedin.com/company/mergeproject](https://www.linkedin.com/company/mergeproject)) to share project-related content, updates, and discussions. We aim to attract stakeholders, researchers, policymakers, media professionals, and members of the general public eager to know more and engage with MERGE. We will consistently share valuable content and foster meaningful conversations to grow our LinkedIn following organically.

Our content strategy includes:

1. **Project updates** (publishing regular posts highlighting the latest developments, achievements, and milestones of the MERGE project, keeping our followers informed about our progress)
2. **Thought leadership** (sharing insights, research findings, and thought-provoking articles related to beyond GDP measures, sustainable development, and climate governance, showcasing our expertise and contributing to thought leadership in the field);
3. **Event announcements** (promoting upcoming events, webinars, workshops, and conferences organised by MERGE or featuring our team members as speakers, providing opportunities for networking and knowledge exchange);
4. **News from the field** (sharing relevant news articles, reports, and publications related to sustainable economics, climate action, and environmental policy, keeping our audience updated on the latest trends and developments in the field).

Implementing this strategy from the start, MERGE has reached 1,377 followers on its LinkedIn (up to 5/2025). Especially, MERGE's posts to announce its new reports received huge traction in terms of engagement rate:

- **D4.1** Survey report on the perceptions on beyond GDP approach (60.5%)
- **D1.3** Summary and review of the linkages between indicators, models, sustainability goals, and policies (52.6%)
- **D1.1** Are Beyond-GDP metrics converging? Consolidation of the measurement of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (52.2%)
- **D4.2** Policy Brief: Public support for Beyond GDP indicators and policy frameworks in the European Union (27.3%)

These results indicate that MERGE's dissemination and communication strategy has attracted interested actors to its work, bringing science-based expertise to the wider community, and amplifying the research's impact beyond MERGE's circle to a boundless pool of researchers, policymakers, social services actors, and the general public.

As the project progresses, we will continue to leverage LinkedIn as a platform to engage with our audience, expand our network, and amplify the project's impact. We will actively monitor the performance of our LinkedIn page, track key metrics such as follower growth and engagement rates, and adjust our strategy as needed to optimise results. Our key performance indicator for LinkedIn is achieving a robust network of connections by the end of the project.

5.5.3. Project website

The website for the MERGE project (<https://mergeproject.eu/>) was launched in April 2024 and has served as a central hub for all stakeholders. It provides comprehensive information about the project's goals, timeline, events and workshops, results, partners, contact details, and funding sources. Designed to be dynamic and adaptable, the website evolves alongside the project's activities, ensuring it remains up-to-date and relevant. Demos Helsinki serves as the website's admin contact, receiving input on the content from all Work Packages (WPS). Visitors experience a user-friendly interface, optimised for various screen sizes and easily discoverable through search engines. Logo and colours, as well as other MERGE outlook-related choices, can be seen in the brand guidelines.

Since April 2024, our website has recorded approximately 8,100 unique visitors. These visitors came from a wide range of countries, including Finland, Italy, Belgium, the U.S., Spain, and the Netherlands. The peak in traffic coincided with new updates on the website, such as reports and events, highlighting the effectiveness of coordinated channels like LinkedIn, newsletters, and other sources in driving engagement towards the website.

5.6. Webinars and Promotional Videos

Webinars and promotional videos are integral components of MERGE's outreach strategy, serving as powerful tools to engage stakeholders and disseminate key project findings. Webinars offer a dynamic platform for interactive discussions, allowing us to connect with a diverse audience of stakeholders, experts, and interested citizens. The themes of the webinars are planned in tandem with the project's activities. All announcements on future webinars will be published on our website and LinkedIn page. Recorded videos are expected to be stored on the MERGE YouTube page.

5.7. Youtube

The key idea for MERGE YouTube content is to serve as a repository for webinars produced throughout the project's span. The aim is to make MERGE content accessible to a wide audience. This approach not only enhances the accessibility of project findings but also maximises the potential for knowledge dissemination and audience engagement across various platforms. The videos will be produced of high quality. Their reach and impact are followed and evaluated to improve the content throughout the project. Last term, MERGE uploaded the record of the kick-off conference on its [YouTube channel](#). Given the length of the video (more than an hour), it was not expected to gain huge traction. However, we plan to explore more short-form videos on this channel to increase outreach for this audio-visual stream of content.

5.8. Media and Press

Media contact in MERGE is done when something relevant is happening in the project. A strategic approach to media engagement within MERGE ensures that interactions with the press and the broader media landscape are carefully timed and purposeful. This is guided by the principle that media contact should not be arbitrary but rather initiated based on noteworthy events or achievements within the project. Such events could

initially include milestones such as the kickoff seminar, the mid-point of MERGE, specific policy-related events, or notable achievements that resonate with the project's aims and objectives. Success in this work happens through good relationships with the media as stakeholders.

Last term, the European mainstream media, EUObserver, covered MERGE's work regarding the letter a group of project leaders sent to the European Commission's President. We believe it opened a channel for closer media collaboration between MERGE and media outlets, informing their readers of the latest twists and turns, developments and opportunities towards a sustainable and inclusive wellbeing for all. We will continue to intensify this stream with the right purpose.

5.9. Monitoring Impacts and KPIs for MERGE

We regularly monitor all KPIs listed in the table below to assess progress, identify potential obstacles, and explore opportunities for refining MERGE messaging. Additionally, this monitoring facilitates accelerating community-building efforts aligned with the targeted KPI achievements.

Table. Merge communication activities and related KPIs.

Communication Activity	Timing	KPIs (mid-project updates)	KPIs (end-of-project goals)
Project website	M3	Over 8100 visitors	Over 12000 visitors
Social media (YouTube, LinkedIn)	M3	Over 1300 followers	Over 2000 followers
Newsletter	Continuous	260 subscribers, 5 sent	Over 400 subscribers, 6 sent
Promotional videos/webinars	Continuous	46 views	Over 1000 views combined
Milestone press releases	After major milestones	1 published	6 published

Media appearances	Continuous	1 outlet	Over 10
Co-creation activities	Continuous (43 in total)		Over 1000 participants
Training sessions	M32, M34, M36		3 held with over 100 participants
Data & policy guidance	M36		Presented to 100 policymakers
MERGE events and conferences	Continuous	Approximately 300 in total	1000 participants in total

6. Results Exploitation Plan

6.1. Plan for exploitation

As outlined in earlier chapters of this CDE plan, MERGE began with a strong emphasis on communication and outreach to raise awareness and generate interest among the public, media, and early collaborators. Early cooperation with other projects and initiatives working on new economic thinking, sustainability, and multidimensional indicators has helped build the foundation for wider engagement and future uptake.

As the project has progressed and core deliverables have begun to take shape, the focus is gradually shifting toward exploitation—ensuring that results are used, translated, and further developed in collaboration with key stakeholders. This CDE plan will continue to evolve accordingly, responding to emerging policy opportunities and stakeholder needs as they become clearer. The MERGE consortium has intentionally analysed these needs through stakeholder engagement embedded across work packages. Based on this, we are preparing to co-develop capacity building materials that reflect both the technical outputs of the project and the practical demands of potential users in policymaking, civil society, and research.

Exploitation activities will include:

- Dialogue and co-creation with selected stakeholders to shape outputs in ways that support real-world applications.
- Development of materials and tools that support integration into policy processes and institutional practice.
- Strategic presentation of project findings in relevant forums to encourage uptake.

- Continued integration of results into academic teaching, public discussion, and thematic networks.

Beyond MERGE, we aim to ensure that the most relevant project outcomes remain accessible, applicable, and influential. This includes supporting their uptake through ongoing partnerships, follow-up projects, and long-term institutional collaboration—helping embed beyond GDP approaches into future economic governance and policy design.

Key exploitable results (KER) continue to build on:

- Synthesis typology (KER1) targeting researchers and policymakers through new research initiatives
- An established network of diverse actors (KER2) targeting policy, technical and civil society actors through active knowledge exchange and new policy initiatives
- Harmonised methodologies for wellbeing and sustainability indicators (KER5) targeting NSIs and modellers through the development of an integrated methodology
- Application of frameworks and indicators (KER6) targeting policy makers and civil society through policy recommendations and advocacy
- Capacity building and methodological support (KER9) targeting all actors through the thorough incorporation of training into existing and new capacity-building programs

6.2. Intellectual property rights

Matters related to the management of knowledge and intellectual property rights (IPR) are defined in the 'Consortium Agreement' (CA) to protect MERGE's results.

Considering the open nature of MERGE's key results and the willingness to share many of them as openly as possible, no major IP and IPR issues are anticipated. The actual background IPR and anticipated foreground IP, as well as the procedures to manage and guard the IP, are elaborated in the consortium agreement.

7. Internal Communication / CDE-plan management

To keep everyone on board with the CDE action at hand, we have been sharing timelines and requests with consortium members. Below attached, you can see a few examples

through which we have communicated internally with the consortium on what the plan is for the upcoming weeks and months.

Timeline Q1/2024

Picture 1. Timeline for Q1/2024

Picture 2. WP reporting at the MERGING meeting 03/2025

We have established the following ways of working to support coordination across the consortium, and they continue to evolve as the project progresses.

1. We utilise the Project's shared Teams space, leveraging its channels and file management, as our central platform for facilitating collaboration, internal communication, and the sharing of materials.
2. We share guidelines on how to use MERGE visuals and templates to ensure consistency and compliance with project branding.
3. We advise the project partners on their obligations in relation to CDE activities, as per the Grant Agreement and Horizon Europe rules.
4. To streamline communication-related efforts, we establish contact points within all work packages, who are responsible for producing and delivering content for the website, newsletters, and social media channels.
5. We regularly discuss communication matters during events such as the MERGING meetings. This approach ensures continuous engagement and alignment among all partners on CDE activities.
6. We iterate our reporting practices to align with sibling projects.

MERGE

Policy pathways to sustainable and inclusive wellbeing

mergeproject.eu

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